

**IMPACT OF FEDERAL GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE AND ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN NIGERIA (1981-2022)**

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of federal government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981-2022. The purpose of federal government expenditure is essentially to stimulate economic growth, however, the extent to which federal government expenditure engender growth has continued to generate theoretical and empirical debate. Conceptual and theoretical literature on federal government expenditure and economic growth were critically reviewed. Empirical evidence on the relationship between the federal government and economic growth were also reviewed. the Federal Government recurrent expenditure on administration has a coefficient of $\beta = -19.56759$ and a p-value of 0.0917, the coefficients of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (FGCSCS) were determined to be $\beta = 22.88605$, with a corresponding p-value of 0.0430, the Federal Government Recurrent spending on social and community services has a coefficient of $\beta = 33.53082$ and a p-value of 0.0034, that the coefficient for Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services (FGRES) is positive, with a p-value of 0.0857. The analytical tool adopted for this study is the Auto Regressive Distribution Lag model and error correction mechanism. Other econometric tests such as unit root and cointegration tests were carried out to determine stationarity of series and long run relationship between federal government and economic growth in Nigeria for the period under study. The bounds test of cointegration revealed the presence of a long run relationship among the variables, while the error correction mechanism indicated a speed of 33.83% convergence to long run equilibrium. The analysis revealed that federal government's capital expenditures on administration, social and community services and economic services have a significant impact on economic growth. Thus, the study establishes that federal capital expenditures impact more on economic growth in Nigeria than recurrent spending during the period under study. It was therefore recommended that the Federal Government of Nigeria through the relevant authorities should allocate a larger portion of its budget to sectors that significantly stimulate and promote growth in productive sectors, thus accelerating the growth of the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: Capital expenditure, Recurrent expenditure, Economic growth, Fiscal Policy.

INTRODUCTION

Like other countries dependent on mineral extraction, Nigeria faces two challenges when formulating fiscal policy: in the long run, the need to ensure that the fiscal stance is compatible with the sustainable use of oil and gas resources, and in the short-to-medium-term, the need to prevent the revenue volatility from spilling over into budget. Fiscal rules could play a role in guiding the sustainable use of resources, taking into account the exhaustibility of resources and intergenerational equity objectives, while aiming at stabilizing expenditure programs at levels consistent with the long-run target for sustainable fiscal stance.

Over the years, there has been a strong deficit bias in fiscal policy caused and enhanced by factors such as large government sectors and non-diversification of the revenue base of the economy driven largely by oil price developments. The revenue-sharing arrangement, whereby about half of oil revenue is allocated to states and local governments, has facilitated an expansion of expenditure programs at the sub-national level, a tendency that has further constrained the ability of the federal government to stabilize overall expenditure. As a result, fiscal volatility has been transmitted to the rest of the economy, with no visible growth performance. The attention toward the government expenditure issues stems mainly from the fact that government expenditure has become so large in recent years in relation to historical experiences. The increase in government expenditure and the subsequent attention to this issue has resulted in more controversy about the impact of government expenditure on economic growth.

Federal government expenditure has risen vastly in naira terms over the years. This is caused by a number of factors which include: cost of public services, technical change, population change, urbanization and growth in per capita income. The federal government has not consistently controlled its expenditure, hence the fiscal deficit. Public expenditure management has been fluctuating for many reasons. Although the government has implemented several potentially useful reforms in public expenditure programming, expenditure decisions and the rationale for expenditure patterns have lacked transparency. Federal government's commitments to spending discipline and adherence to rules and laid down procedures are both weak and irregular.

In Nigeria, federal government expenditure has continued to rise due to the huge receipts from production and sales of crude oil, and the increased demand for public goods.

Unfortunately, rising federal government expenditure has not translated to meaningful growth and development, as Nigeria ranks among the poorest countries in the world. In addition, many Nigerians have continued to wallow in abject poverty, while so many live below the poverty line.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

In Nigeria, federal government expenditure has continued to rise due to the huge receipts from production and sales of crude oil, and the increased demand for public goods. Unfortunately, rising federal government expenditure has not translated to meaningful growth and development, as Nigeria ranks among the poorest countries in the world. In addition, many Nigerians have continued to wallow in abject poverty, while so many live below the poverty line. Added to this is dilapidated infrastructure (especially roads and power supply) that has led to the collapse of many industries, including high level of unemployment. The economic problem is how to stimulate growth in order to increase the standard of living in the country.

The data of federal government budgetary allocation to its components of public expenditure indicated a steady increase from 1984-1997. An astronomical increase in the budgetary allocation of the variables was recorded from 1999-2021 except for a few years where there was a drop. However, these increase in allocation has not translated into meaningful impact on these sectors and the economy. The above scenario therefore, has necessitated this research to assess the impact of Federal Government Expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Against the background of difficulties associated with federal government achieving its desired goals, this study attempts to answer the following questions:

- i) What is the impact of Federal Government capital and recurrent expenditure on administration on economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii) How does Federal Government capital and recurrent expenditure on social and community services impact on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iii) To what extent does Federal Government capital and recurrent expenditure on economic services impact on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iv) How does Federal Government capital and recurrent expenditure on transfer payment on economic growth in Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between government expenditure and economic growth has continued to generate series of debate among scholars. Many researchers have attempted to examine the effect of government expenditure on economic growth. Some scholars argued that increase in government socio-economic and physical infrastructure encourages economic growth. For example, government expenditure on health and education raises the productivity of labour and increases growth of national output. Similarly, expenditure on infrastructure such as roads, communications, power, etc., reduces production costs and increases private sector investment and profitability of firms, thus, fostering economic growth. Supporting this view are scholars such as Abdullahi (2000), Al-yousif (2000), Ranjan & Shama (2008) and Cooraay (2009), who concluded that expansion of government expenditure contributes positively to economic growth.

Nurudeen & Usman (2010) used the co-integration and error correction methods to analyse the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth for the period 1970-2008. The estimation results revealed that the explanatory variables jointly account for approximately 58.96% changes in economic growth. The estimation results showed that the variables - total expenditure, total recurrent expenditure, expenditure on transport and communication, education and health, including inflation and overall fiscal balance - are statistically significant in explaining changes in economic growth.

Ighodaro & Okiakhi (2010) used time series data for the period 1961 to 2007 and applied cointegration and Ganger causality test to examine federal government expenditure disaggregated into general administration and community services in Nigeria. The result revealed a negative impact of the government on economic growth. Research conducted by Olawunmi & Ayinla (2007) on government expenditure and Nigerian economic growth using the Ordinary Least Square method to analysed the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria found that deficit financing recorded over a period of 1980-2004 has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Loto (2011) investigated the impact of sectoral government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1980-2008 and using cointegration technique and Error Correction Model. The result inferred that in the short run, expenditure in agriculture and education were negatively related to economic growth. However, expenditure on health, national security, transportation, and communication were positively related to economic growth, though the

impacts were not statistically significant. Ehiogu, Okezie and Chinedu (2013) examined the commitment of the federal government of Nigeria to education through her budgetary allocations and also assessed the causal relationship between the government expenditure on education and economic growth from 1981-2011 using time series data. The result revealed that expenditure on education is positively related to the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) while gross fixed capital formation is negatively related to GDP.

Nworji, Okwu, Obowuru and Nworji (2012) examined the effect of public expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1970 – 2009. The tool of analysis was the OLS multiple regression model specified on perceived causal relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. The time series data included in the model were those on gross domestic product (GDP), and various components of government expenditure. Onifade et al (2020) studied the impact of federal government expenditures on economic growth with respect to capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure and government fiscal expansion in the Nigerian economy. The findings supported the existence of a level relationship between public spending indicators and economic growth in Nigeria. Recurrent expenditure of the federal government was found to have a negative impact on economic growth, while the positive impacts of public capital expenditure were not significant to economic growth over the period. The impact of federal government expenditure on economic growth is a controversial and long-standing topic in economic theory, empirical research, and economic policymaking.

Onifade et al (2020) studied the impact of federal government expenditures on economic growth with respect to capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure and government fiscal expansion in the Nigerian economy, carrying out the impact analysis using annual time-series data from 1981-2017. The findings supported the existence of a level relationship between public spending indicators and economic growth in Nigeria. Recurrent expenditure of the federal government was found to have a negative impact on economic growth, while the positive impacts of public capital expenditure were not significant to economic growth over the period.

Nimenibo and Samuel (2020) examined the government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria from 1985-2015. The study revealed that government recurrent expenditure has a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Okpabi, Ijuo and Akiri (2021) examined the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria from

1984-2015, the empirical results showed that public expenditure has a significant positive impact on the economy of Nigeria in the long run and an insignificant impact in the short-run.

FIGURE 1: THEORETICAL / CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

METHODOLOGY

The method of regression used in this study is Auto Regressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) model applied within the context of multiple regression.

ARDL Model Specification

$$\Delta GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta GDP_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta FGCA_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \Delta FGRA_{t-1} + \alpha_4 \Delta FGSCSC_{t-1} + \alpha_5 \Delta FGRSCS_{t-1} + \alpha_6 \Delta FGCE_{t-1} + \alpha_7 \Delta FGRES_{t-1} + \alpha_8 \Delta FGCTR_{t-1} + \alpha_9 \Delta FGRTR_{t-1}$$

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_{t-1} + \beta_2 FGCA_{t-1} + \beta_3 FGRA_{t-1} + \beta_4 FGSCSC_{t-1} + \beta_5 FGRSCS_{t-1} + \beta_6 FGCE_{t-1} + \beta_7 FGRES_{t-1} + \beta_8 FGCTR_{t-1} + \beta_9 FGRTR_{t-1} + \phi z_{t-1} + U_t$$

GDP_t = Gross Domestic Product proxy for Economic Growth at time t

$FGCA_t$ = Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Administration at time t

$FGRA_t$ = Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Administration at time t

$FGSCSC_t$ = Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services at time t

$FGRSCS_t$ = Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services at time t

$FGCE_t$ = Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services at time t

$FGRES_t$ = Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services at time t

$FGRTR_t$ = Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Transfer Payment at time t , and

$FGCTR_t$ = Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Transfer Payment at time t

α_0 = Constant term

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7, \alpha_8$ and α_9 = short-run coefficients of federal government expenditure (capital and recurrent)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8$ and β_9 = Long-run coefficients of federal government expenditure (capital and recurrent)

Δ = Change or difference factor

Φ = Coefficient of the error correction model

z = error correction model variable

$t-1$ = Lag term

U_t = Error term

Descriptive Statistics

	<i>GDP</i>	<i>FGRA</i>	<i>FGC</i> <i>A</i>	<i>FGRS</i> <i>CS</i>	<i>FGCS</i> <i>CS</i>	<i>FGR</i> <i>ES</i>	<i>FGCE</i> <i>S</i>	<i>FGRT</i> <i>R</i>	<i>FGC</i> <i>TR</i>
Mean	38589.547	590.003	186.439	365.565	75.000	153.470	280.638	903.186	101.961
Standard Deviation	20854.419	730.515	216.633	492.526	92.367	187.043	323.487	1421.700	143.027
Kurtosis	-1.379	0.365	0.012	0.448	2.020	-0.46	2.706	5.738	3.452
Skewness	0.547	1.179	0.990	1.275	1.493	0.957	1.606	2.347	1.925
Minimum	16048.310	0.900	0.263	0.290	0.238	0.170	0.656	3.390	0.000
Maximum	74639.470	2456.331	789.806	1628.990	377.259	562.753	1369.662	6355.900	597.094
Count	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42

Source: Author's Computation using Eviews 10

The descriptive data indicate that the mean GDP for the duration of this study is N38589.547 billion. The GDP range is from N16048.310 billion to N74639.470 billion, with a standard deviation of N20854.419 billion. The mean FGRA is N590.003. The FGRA ranges from N0.900 to N2456.331, with a standard deviation of N730.515. The FGCA exhibited an average value of N186.439 billion, with a minimum value of N0.263 billion and a maximum value of N789.806 billion. The standard deviation was calculated to be N216.633 billion.

The FGRSCS had an average value of N365.565 billion, with the minimum and greatest values being N0.290 billion and N1628.990 billion, respectively. The standard deviation is N492.526 billion. The FGCS had an average value of N75.000 billion, with the minimum and greatest values being N0.238 and N377.259 billion, respectively. The standard deviation is N92.367. The mean FGRES is N153.470, with a minimum value of N0.170 and a maximum value of N562.753. The standard deviation is N187.043. The FGCE had an average value of N280.638 billion, ranging from a minimum of N0.656 billion to a maximum of N1369.662 billion. The standard deviation of the FGCE was N323.487 billion. The FGRTR exhibited an average value of N903.186 billion, with a minimum value of N3.390 billion and a maximum value of N6355.900 billion. The standard deviation is

N1421.719 billion. The FGCTR had an average value of N101.961 billion, with the minimum and maximum values being N0.000 and N597.094 billion respectively. The standard deviation is N143.027.

The economic implication of this result is that the spending of Federal Government has been too low to impact on economic growth over the last 42 years. Despite huge spending by the Federal Government of Nigeria both on current and capital expenditure in Administration, Social and Community Services, Economic Services, and Transfer Payment on Economic, the spending has not translated into meaningful economic growth.

Normality Test

The time series data gathered for this investigation underwent a normality test. This is done to fulfill one of the assumptions of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The result of the normality test is shown in Figure 1.

Source: Eviews 10

The analysis depicted in the above figure indicates that the Jarque-Bera probability value of 0.8341 is above the significance level of 0.05. This outcome indicates that the data follows a normal distribution.

Bounds Co-integration Test

A Bounds Test was undertaken to ascertain the presence of cointegration among the variables.

Bounds test of Co-integration Result

F-Bounds Test	Null Hypothesis:		No. levels relationship	
	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	7.965433	10%	2.26	3.34
K	8	5%	2.55	3.68
		2.5%	2.82	4.02
		1%	3.15	4.43

The results of the bounds co-integration test, indicate that the null hypothesis is rejected at a significance level of 5%. The estimated F-statistic of 7.965433 surpasses the lower and upper critical bound values for significance levels of 10%, 5%, 2.5%, and 1%. This indicates the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. The implication of this result is that the model specified in this study was interpreted in terms of short-run and long-run impacts of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on the variables on economic growth in Nigeria.

Long-Run and Short-Run ARDL Estimation

The results of the ARDL model for the long-run and short-run effects of various factors, such as Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Administration, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Administration, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Transfer Payment, and Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Transfer Payment, on economic growth in Nigeria are presented in Table below.

Short-run and Long-run Results

Variables	Coefficient	P-value
SHORT-RUN		
$\Delta GDP(-1)$	-0.338253	0.0014**
$\Delta(FGCA)$	19.09458	0.0044**
$\Delta(FGRA)$	-1.872937	0.5325
$\Delta(FGCES)$	-4.500326	0.1993
$\Delta(FGRES)$	-1.425477	0.7356
$\Delta(FGCSCS)$	22.88605	0.0430**
$\Delta(FGRSCS)$	1.763099	0.7032
$\Delta(FGCTR)$	-6.391466	0.1100
$\Delta(FGRTR)$	-1.582630	0.0122**
$ECM(-1)$	-0.338253	0.0000**
LONG-RUN		
$(FGCA)$	56.45062	0.0000**
$(FGRA)$	-19.56759	0.0917
$(FGCES)$	-25.22035	0.0492**
$(FGRES)$	21.50384	0.0857
$(FGCSCS)$	120.0149	0.0348**
$(FGRSCS)$	33.53082	0.0034**
$(FGCTR)$	-18.89553	0.1233
$(FGRTR)$	-4.678837	0.0074**
R^2	0.801808	
$Durbin-Watson$	1.967	
$F-stat$	19.07218	0.0000**

Dependent variable: GDP

** 5%

The table above presents the outcomes of the ARDL analysis, showing the Error Correction Model (ECM) as well as the short-term and long-term effects. According to the error correction equation, it is anticipated to have a negative value, be less than one, and be statistically significant at a 5% level. The ECM result fully satisfied the 100% requirement

for what is anticipated from the ECM. The ECM value in this investigation is -33.83%, indicating a negative, statistically significant result that is less than one. The data demonstrates that equilibrium is rectified or reinstated in the subsequent year at a rate of 33.83%, signifying a sluggish pace of adjustment.

The short-term analysis reveals that the coefficients of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Administration (FGCA) are $\beta = 19.09458$, with a corresponding p-value of 0.0044. The findings indicate that the Federal Government's capital expenditure on administration has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth, with a significance level of 5%. In the long run, the Federal Government's capital expenditure on administration has a coefficient of $\beta = 56.45062$ and a p-value of 0.0000. Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Administration (FGRA) has coefficients with a value of $\beta = -1.872937$ and a p-value of 0.5325. In the long run, the Federal Government's recurrent expenditure on administration has a coefficient of $\beta = -19.56759$ and a p-value of 0.0917, similar to the short-run outcome. The data also demonstrates that Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Administration has a detrimental and statistically negligible effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The findings indicate that the allocation of Federal Government funds towards administrative expenses has not demonstrated any potential for fostering economic growth in Nigeria.

In addition, in the near term, the coefficients of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (FGSCS) were determined to be $\beta = 22.88605$, with a corresponding p-value of 0.0430. The findings indicate that the Federal Government's investment in Social and Community Services has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth, with a significance level of 5%. The coefficient value of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services aligns with the anticipated expectation, as it is projected to be both positive and large. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that the Federal Government's Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services had a coefficient of $\beta = 120.0149$ and a p-value of 0.0348. The data also demonstrates that the Federal Government's investment in Social and Community Services has a substantial and beneficial effect on Nigeria's economic growth. This conclusion confirms the initial anticipation that an increase in Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services will lead to economic growth in Nigeria.

The analysis of Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services (FGRSCS) in the short-run revealed a coefficient of $\beta = 1.763099$ and a p-value of 0.7032. The findings indicate that the impact of Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services on economic development is favourable, but statistically inconsequential at a significance level of 5%. The outcome partially aligned with the anticipated a priori assumption of being positive and significant, but instead it was positive and lacked significance. Contrarily, over a long period of time, the Federal Government's ongoing spending on social and community services has a coefficient of $\beta=33.53082$ and a p-value of 0.0034. The observed outcome does not align with the anticipated expectation, which was predicted to be both positive and significant. Increasing the Federal Government's recurrent expenditure on social and community services in Nigeria will lead to a corresponding boost in economic growth.

The Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCES) has a negligible and adverse effect on economic growth. The coefficient value of Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCES) did not align with the expected positive and significant value. However, over time, it was discovered that Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (FGCES) had a considerable and detrimental effect on economic growth. This suggests that the Federal Government's investment in economic services has not been successful in promoting economic growth in Nigeria, leading to a constant decline in both the short-term and long-term.

The study revealed that the Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services (FGRES) had a negative impact on economic growth. The outcome does not align with the anticipated expectation, as it was supposed to be both positive and statistically significant. However, over time, it was determined that the effect of Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services (FGRES) on economic growth was both positive and not significant. Although there may be different outcomes in both the short-term and long-term, it can be concluded that Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services has a limited impact on economic growth in Nigeria. While yielding favourable outcomes in the long-term, it has adverse effects in the short-term.

The study indicated that the Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Transfer Payment (FGCTR) has a negative and statistically insignificant impact on economic growth,

both in the short-run and long-run. This outcome did not align with the initial expectation, indicating that the FGCTR's impact on economic growth in Nigeria throughout the study period was not successful in promoting economic growth in the country. Results of the study also indicated that the Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Transfer Payment (FGRTR) has a negative and considerable influence on economic growth, both in the short-run and long-run. The outcome did not align with the anticipated a priori expectation, which was predicted to be both positive and significant. This indicates that FGRTR in Nigeria throughout the study period has not effectively led to economic growth in the country.

The coefficient of determination, $r^2 = 0.8018$, indicates that 80.2% of the variation in economic growth in Nigeria can be attributed to changes in the following factors: Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Administration, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Administration, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Economic Services, Federal Government Capital Expenditure on Transfer Payment, and Federal Government Recurrent Expenditure on Transfer Payment. The ARDL model in this investigation was determined to be properly stated, as evidenced by the F-statistic's p-value of 0.000.

Stability Test

The stability test is graphically represented, indicating that stability is achieved when the middle line remains within the bounds of the two parallel lines, whereas deviation from these lines implies instability. **Stability Test Result**

The stability test was conducted to assess the temporal consistency of the relationship between the variables. The diagram illustrates that the central line remained parallel to the two adjacent lines without any deviation. This indicates that the link between the variables remained consistent.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the impact of federal government spending on the Nigerian economy. The Federal Government's capital expenditure on administration has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria; second, the Federal Government's capital expenditure on social and community services also has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria; and the Federal Government's capital expenditure on economic services also has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study found that the Federal Government's recurring spending on social and community services had a substantial influence on economic growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, the Federal Government's recurring spending on transfer payments also has a major impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Again, the study found that the Federal Government's recurrent expenditure on administration, economic services, and capital expenditure on transfer payment did not have a significant influence on economic growth in Nigeria. The analysis suggests that capital expenditures by the federal government had a greater impact on economic growth in Nigeria than recurrent spending throughout the specified period.

RECOMMENDATION

To maintain economic growth, the federal government of Nigeria must consistently boost spending through the budgetary allocation on administration by more than N0.263 billion. Lower government spending cannot lead to good economic growth. The spending must also be carried out with transparency. Hence, the Federal Government of Nigeria should provide diligent oversight and accurate record-keeping of all funds allocated for recurring administrative spending, particularly by dedicated auditors from the Ministry of Finance and office of the Auditor General of the Federation.

The Federal Government of Nigeria should maintain spending on social and community services in Nigeria because of its positive multiplier impact on economic growth. The Federal Ministry of Health and Social Welfare should ensure that high quality healthcare and vital services are provided to Nigerians. The Federal Government of Nigeria should exercise prudence when allocating resources to social and community services, particularly recurring expenses. They should not prioritize excessive capital spending at the expense of recurrent expenses. To achieve equilibrium, an equivalent level of investment in recurrent expenses should be allocated as capital expenses by the Budget Office of the Federation.

The Federal Government of Nigeria should persist in upholding and supporting its expenditure on economic services such as education and the health sector in Nigeria. Improving educational infrastructure, improved welfare packages to lecturers and researchers and medical personnel in the hospital would stimulate robust economic expansion. A well-educated and healthy people contribute to economic progress. The Federal Government of Nigeria's recurring expenditure on economic services had an insignificant impact on economic growth in Nigeria, because of inadequate funding and insufficient support provided to teachers, lecturers, health personnel, and security authorities. The Federal Government of Nigeria should enhance the well-being of educators, professors, health care professionals, and security personnel. Sufficient funds should be allocated to the remuneration of these specific groups of government employees.

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APPENDIX A: DATA PRESENTATION

year	GDP	FGRA	FGRSC S	FGRE S	FGRTR	FGC A	FGCES	FGCSC S	FGCTR
1981	19549.56	0.91	0.29	0.18	3.46	0.72	3.63	1.30	0.92
1982	18211.27	1.04	0.33	0.2	3.93	0.39	2.54	0.97	2.52
1983	16228.81	0.9	0.29	0.17	3.39	1.10	2.29	1.03	0.47
1984	16048.31	1.1	0.35	0.21	4.16	0.26	0.66	0.24	2.94
1985	16997.52	1.43	0.46	0.27	5.41	0.46	0.89	1.15	2.96
1986	17007.77	1.45	0.47	0.28	5.5	0.26	1.10	0.66	6.51
1987	17552.1	3.83	0.3	0.69	10.81	1.82	2.16	0.62	1.78
1988	18839.55	5.78	2.11	1.22	10.3	1.90	2.13	1.73	2.59
1989	19201.16	6.27	4.23	1.42	14.07	2.62	3.93	1.84	6.65
1990	21462.73	6.54	3.4	1.61	24.67	2.92	3.49	2.10	15.55
1991	21539.61	6.95	2.68	1.3	27.31	3.35	3.15	1.49	20.36
1992	22537.1	8.68	1.34	3.08	39.93	5.12	2.34	2.13	30.18
1993	22078.07	30.57	14.66	7.75	83.75	8.08	18.34	3.58	24.50
1994	21676.85	20.54	10.09	3.91	55.44	8.79	27.10	4.99	30.04
1995	21660.49	28.76	13.82	5.92	79.13	13.34	43.15	9.22	55.44
1996	22568.87	47.12	17.69	5.84	53.64	14.86	117.83	8.66	71.58
1997	23231.12	56.16	22.06	6.2	74.12	49.55	169.61	6.90	43.59

1998	23829.7 6	50.68	21.44	11.57	94.4	35.27	200.86	23.37	49.52
1999	23967.5 9	183.64	71.37	87.08	107.58	42.74	323.58	17.25	114.46
2000	25169.5 4	144.53	84.79	28.59	203.69	53.28	111.51	27.97	46.70
2001	26658.6 2	180.80	79.63	53.01	265.86	49.25	259.76	53.34	76.35
2002	30745.1 9	266.51	152.19	52.95	225.15	73.58	215.33	32.47	0.00
2003	33004.8	307.97	102.61	96.07	477.65	87.96	97.98	55.74	0.01
2004	36057.7 4	306.80	134.40	58.90	610.70	137.7 7	167.72	30.03	15.73
2005	38378.8	434.70	151.70	64.20	670.70	171.5 7	265.03	71.36	11.50
2006	40703.6 8	522.30	194.20	79.70	594.00	185.2 2	262.21	78.68	26.27
2007	43385.8 8	626.36	256.67	179.07	527.17	226.9 7	358.38	150.90	23.04
2008	46320.0 1	731.02	332.93	313.75	739.66	287.1 0	504.29	152.17	17.33
2009	50042.3 6	714.42	354.19	423.61	635.75	279.5 1	506.01	144.93	210.20
2010	54612.2 6	1,117.4 4	550.90	562.75	878.34	306.4 1	412.20	151.77	59.70
2011	57511.0 4	1,262.4 0	785.44	310.50	956.18	333.3 1	386.40	92.85	207.50
2012	59929.8 9	1,159.4 0	790.06	230.10	1,145.6 0	360.2 1	320.90	97.40	265.90
2013	63218.7 2	1,111.8 0	844.10	291.20	1,441.9 0	387.1 1	505.77	154.71	164.27
2014	67152.7 9	992.84	774.77	266.40	1,392.9 3	414.0 1	393.45	111.29	48.75
2015	69023.9 3	1,228.9 9	807.59	275.36	1,520.0 1	440.9 2	348.75	82.98	159.82

2016	67931.2 4	1,277.0 0	775.55	255.78	1,851.7 7	467.8 2	278.95	68.80	158.14
2017	68490.9 8	1,324.3 0	931.68	334.89	2,189.1 2	494.7 2	542.19	167.66	203.51
2018	69799.9 4	1,584.0 6	1,083.73	372.55	2,634.8 5	446.2 5	753.49	203.42	278.94
2019	71387.8 3	2,104.4 7	1,393.08	478.86	3,018.3 7	591.2 6	994.19	264.69	438.86
2020	70014.3 7	2,294.8 8	1,519.12	522.19	3,854.2 0	417.1 4	701.40	186.74	309.61
2021	72393.6 7	2,168.4 5	1,438.07	495.32	5,043.3 0	635.7 3	1,102.4 6	303.66	480.61
2022	74639.4 7	2,456.3 3	1628.99	561.08	6355.90	789.8 1	1,369.6 6	377.26	597.09